

Knowledge Sharing Practices as a Correlate of Service Delivery of Polytechnic Library Staff in South-West, Nigeria

Ganiyu Idowu Buhari¹, **Jamiu Adewale Abdulsalam**², **Adebayo Afolabi Olajide**³

Saheed Oluwasegun Oyewole⁴, **Omolade Iyabo Musa**⁵, **Sikirat Oluwakemi Balogun**⁶

¹The Library, Federal Polytechnic, Ede, Nigeria

²Federal University, Oye-Ekiti, Ekiti State

³University Library, Precious Cornerstone University, Ibadan

⁴Department of Library Science, University of Ilesha, Osun State.

⁵Adeleke University, Ede, Osun State

⁶Gerar University of Medical Science, Imope-Ijebu, Ogun State

Corresponding author email: ganibuhari@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

Background: This study investigates the level of knowledge sharing practices among staff in polytechnic libraries in South-West, Nigeria. Polytechnic libraries are essential for teaching, learning, and research support, and the quality of their services is influenced by knowledge sharing, which fosters innovation, problem-solving, and user satisfaction through the exchange of experiences, expertise, and skills.

Method: A quantitative approach with a survey research design was adopted. The study population comprised 325 professional and para-professional library staff from 23 public polytechnic libraries in South-West, Nigeria. A total enumeration sampling technique was used, with 325 questionnaires distributed and 266 valid responses retrieved (response rate: 81.85%). Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics (mean) and inferential statistics (Pearson correlation) to assess relationships.

Findings/Results: The findings revealed a moderately high level of knowledge sharing practices among polytechnic library staff ($M = 2.5514$). A statistically significant positive correlation was found between knowledge sharing and service delivery ($r = 0.609$, $p < 0.05$), indicating that knowledge sharing enhances the quality of library services.

Implications: The results suggest that knowledge sharing practices significantly contribute to improved service delivery in polytechnic libraries. Encouraging a culture of knowledge exchange can enhance innovation, problem-solving, and user satisfaction, thereby strengthening library services.

Conclusion: The study concludes that knowledge sharing practices are moderately high among polytechnic library staff in South-West, Nigeria, and are significantly correlated with improved service delivery. A sustained culture of knowledge sharing is essential for sustainable service quality.

Recommendations: The study recommends sustaining and increasing the current level of knowledge sharing practices among polytechnic library staff to ensure improved and sustainable service delivery.

Key words: Knowledge-sharing practice, service delivery, polytechnic libraries, library staff

INTRODUCTION

In the current global community, survival of any organisation depends on the physical resources available to them. One of such important resources required by every organisation to weather the competitive environment is knowledge. The world today is witnessing rapid changes and developments which have resulted in the emergence of new terms and concepts that focus primarily on knowledge as an important resource and an element of survival and competitiveness (Antara et al., 2024). Growth, development, profitability and sustainability of any organisation are hinged largely on available knowledge within the organisation and the ability of employees to exchange such knowledge with one another within the same organisation, either close or distant geographical boundaries. In an attempt to effectively utilise and preserve such knowledge from leaving the organisation, the process of knowledge sharing practices, which is an integral part of knowledge management, comes into play. The process of effectively exploring, providing, utilising, transferring, expanding, sharing and preserving knowledge can be termed as knowledge management. However, the most prominent component of knowledge management is the process of knowledge sharing, which allows employees to transfer and exchange knowledge among themselves to enable them perform their work better, and thus achieve organisational goals (Antara et al., 2024). From the perspective of its function, knowledge sharing practices, according to Shehab et al. (2023), is an essential resource for effectively implementing essential business functions. Since service delivery has been identified as the major function of any organisation to achieve its goals and objective, then effective knowledge sharing practices most often lead to effective service delivery which is a critical factor in achieving national growth, development and citizen's well-being.

Knowledge-sharing practices is a very important means and method through which employees contribute what they know to the organisation, brainstorm together with others for new ideas and eventually resulting into positive advantage for the organization (Vij & Farooq, 2014). Knowledge-sharing practice, according to Zamiri and Ali (2024), is an idea sharing, provide insights, sharing of experiences and expertise among individuals or groups which involves the transmission of knowledge for purpose of deepening the collective understanding of people and capabilities in an organisation or the society at large.

In his own contribution, Wilson (2020) described knowledge-sharing practice as a set of behavioural activities involving sharing of knowledge and expertise among members of an organisation to facilitate its effectiveness. Similarly, Rosendaal and Frankema (2013) considered knowledge-sharing practices as interaction within a particular group of people with the aim of facilitating learning and improving the group's capacity to obtain desired purpose. Anna and Puspitasari (2013) described knowledge-sharing practices as an inclusive method of every one bringing a cake and going back with bigger cakes. The issue of knowledge-sharing practices in the academic library is gaining momentum as librarians begin to recognise the importance of the knowledge-sharing practices to the effectiveness and efficiency of their service delivery.

Wang and Wang (2012), revealed that knowledge sharing practices have influenced organisations performance positively through various improvements in certain critical areas of such organisations. Knowledge sharing enables employees to learn from each other, apply new knowledge to their work, and ultimately enhance their productivity and effectiveness (Oyoo,

2019). Therefore, fostering a culture of knowledge sharing practice is crucial for improving employee performance and driving overall organisational performance. (Wen & Ma, 2021). Today's organisational success therefore depends, largely more than ever before, on the efficiency and effectiveness of its knowledge-sharing practices (Wang et al., 2016).

The essence of knowledge sharing practices within and outside the library, according to Islam et al. (2014), is to make the available knowledge accessible to all librarians and information personnel with the focus of improving their service delivery. Knowledge-sharing practices among librarians will help them to perform better in their information service delivery to users as a result of sharing insights and experiences and thus put libraries especially academic ones in a proper stead to promptly meet their clients' information needs.

Academic libraries are set up to provide information services which the users are able to explore, evaluate and access in diverse formats. Maina et al. (2017) opine that academic libraries in tertiary education are meant to provide information resources and services in diverse forms and quantities to support teaching, learning and development of the institution. They further stated that the main duty of academic libraries is to provide all necessary information services needed by its diverse users. With the developments in the library in recent years especially in the area of adoption and application of information and communication technology for operational services and service delivery, the librarians are not expected to be passive but rather take an active role. As the say goes, no one is an island to himself, this properly explains the need for togetherness and team spirit among librarians to serve their clients satisfactorily. This team spirit underscores the importance of knowledge sharing practices to facilitate the service delivery of librarians in academic libraries.

Service delivery, according to Martins and Ledimo (2015), referred to the actual delivery of a service and products to the customer or clients. It is concerned with the where, when, and how a service product is delivered to the customer based on the level of satisfaction that the customer perceives. Yaya and Adeko (2024) asserted that service delivery is an integral part of the activities that must be regularly performed by the personnel of any library, and that as a vital component of academic libraries; it plays a crucial role in supporting their overall mission and goals. They then identified the factors that could boost service delivery in the academic libraries to include quality of library services, user satisfaction, user engagement, staff performance, access to information, library usage, and the academic performance of students. To facilitate effective service delivery that would meet users' expectation in the academic libraries, these identified factors need to be considered as the librarians performed their duties. For a library to be described as meeting the objectives and goals of setting it up there is the need for such library to deliver services that meet the yearnings and aspirations of both staff and students. Such a service that satisfies the need of users can be termed and described as quality or effective service delivery. Attainment of efficient service delivery does not just happen in an organisation, it is based on so many factors. Quality service delivery does not depend only on available infrastructures or tangible facilities possessed by libraries as service organisations but it is concerned with the connection and value that customers can derive from the infrastructure and tangible assets through the help or assistance of the library staff. It is on the basis of this that the study investigated knowledge sharing practices as correlate of service delivery among polytechnic library staff in South-west, Nigeria.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objectives of this study are to:

1. determine the level of knowledge sharing practices among staff working with polytechnic libraries in South-west, Nigeria
2. investigate the influence of knowledge-sharing practices on the service delivery of polytechnic library staff in South-west, Nigeria

HYPOTHESIS

There is no significant relationship between knowledge-sharing practices and service delivery among staff working with polytechnic libraries in South-west, Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

The methodology adopted for the study is descriptive survey research design of quantitative approach. The population of the study consisted of 325 polytechnic library staff from the 23 Public polytechnics in the South-west geopolitical zone of Nigeria. The South-west geo-political zone consists of Ekiti, Lagos, Ogun, Ondo, Osun and Oyo States. Due to manageable size of the population, total enumeration sampling technique was adopted. Quantitative data was collected through the use of questionnaire titled “Knowledge sharing practices and service delivery”. The instrument used for the study was validated through a reliability analysis using split half method and was administered on 30 library staff working in two polytechnics that are not part of the research area of the study. The result showed Cronbach-Alpha reliability coefficients of 0.78.

Copies of the questionnaire were distributed to all the 325 library staff as respondents, but only 266 copies (81.8%) were found usable after retrieval. Data collected through the questionnaire were analysed quantitatively using the descriptive and inferential statistics of percentages, means and standard deviation, while Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation was used to test the one null hypothesis of this research.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

The understanding of knowledge and awareness of its significance in organisation could be credited majorly to Drucker (Andreeva & Kianto, 2012). This understanding and awareness is a precursor to knowledge-sharing practices. As organisations grow and evolve in their various processes of operation, there is the likelihood of employees becoming better at what they do and how they do it. This level of competence and better understanding of the running and operation of the organisation can be termed organisational knowledge of the establishment. It is a valuable asset that must be recognised, harnessed, shared and preserved.

Bessick and Naicker (2013) attested that any organisation that fails to protect its knowledge through documented business process is at a great risk. However, mentoring, storytelling and demonstration have been acknowledged as the best ways to preserve and share tacit knowledge apart from the idea of documented processes for sharing knowledge.

Knowledge sharing has been defined by various authors such that there has not been a consensus on its definition. Lin (2015) defined knowledge sharing practices as common beliefs or regular practices by which employees of a department or organisation exchange knowledge, experiences and skills among themselves. Knowledge sharing practices are very important means and methods through which employees contribute what they know to the organisation, brainstorm together with others for new ideas and eventually resulting into positive advantage for the organization (Vij & Farooq, 2014).

Knowledge-sharing, according to Zamiri and Ali (2024), is an idea sharing, insights provision, sharing of experiences and expertise among individuals or groups which involves the transmission of knowledge for purpose of deepening the collective understanding of people and capabilities in an organisation or the society at large. In his own contribution, Wilson (2020) described knowledge sharing as a set of behavioural activities involving sharing of knowledge and expertise among members of an organisation to facilitate its effectiveness.

According to Rutten, Blaas-Franken and Martin (2016), knowledge sharing is employees' enthusiasm to share what they know with other members of the organisation. Creation of novel knowledge by way of exchanging tacit and explicit knowledge was how Razmerita et al. (2016) defined knowledge-sharing practices. Knowledge sharing practice as stated by Ma et al, (2014), is a method of sharing knowledge involving two people with one regarded as owner and the other as receiver but through effective communication are able to share the knowledge.

Three different modes or forms of sharing knowledge have been established in the literature, they are: individual level knowledge-sharing practices. According to Rowley and Fullwood (2017), this is knowledge-sharing practices between just two people at personal level which can be for the purpose of the organisation or to improve individual's competence. The second mode is group/team/unit level knowledge-sharing practices. This is sharing of knowledge based on some people with common characteristics. The characteristics can be professional, technical or otherwise but there is a common denominator among them and the sharing takes place as group(s). The third one is the organisational level of knowledge-sharing practices. This is sharing knowledge at the level of organisation (Rowley & Fullwood, 2017).

In a study conducted by Imam and Ebiefung (2022) on knowledge sharing as a determinant of information service delivery by library personnel in federal universities in South-West, Nigeria, it was found that knowledge sharing ($r = .561$; $p < 0.05$) has significant positive relationship with information service. A study by Abdulsalam et al. (2025) on knowledge sharing and research output of the librarians in the federal universities revealed that knowledge sharing by librarians can be categorized into two broad groups; written/explicit knowledge and personal/tacit knowledge. As far as written/explicit knowledge is concerned, most respondents indicated that they generate ideas based on social media pages and databases (mean = 3.46) and share knowledge based on published articles in university journals, magazines, or newsletters (mean = 3.13). The weighted average was 2.69 which was greater than the criterion mean. As a result, ideas obtained in social media and knowledge obtained in published articles in university journals, magazines, or newsletters are the most common forms of explicit knowledge among the majority of librarians in federal universities in South-west Nigeria.

Izu (2020) had carried out a research on the knowledge sharing among employees at Delta State University Library. The findings showed that, despite the absence of a formal knowledge-sharing system, it played a significant role in enhancing service delivery. Illustrated through the delivery of correct and punctual services, learning through best library practices, repeating errors and responding to job-related issues. Nevertheless, the lack of knowledge sharing culture was found to be one of the major obstacles to successful co-operation in the library.

In their study, Santosh and Panda (2016) examined knowledge sharing among librarians of a Mega Open University and discovered that knowledge sharing, as voluntary, was less favored by the participants. Nevertheless, publishing was the most preferred knowledge sharing approach in networks. In a study of knowledge sharing practices among African health sciences librarians, by Olayemi and Olayemi (2021), the results showed that the types of knowledge most commonly exchanged by respondents were information on conferences, workshops, and seminars as well as information on new trends and technologies in librarianship. However the frequency of knowledge sharing among respondents revealed a low level of knowledge sharing practices as they engaged in their knowledge occasionally (35.8%), daily (34.0%), several times a month (13.2%), monthly (9.4%), or (7.5%) weekly.

Digital era has now brought about great improvements in the service delivery of academic libraries. The impact of technologies has also led to new demands from users and has therefore challenged librarians to be up and down in meeting the demands of 21st century users. Maina et al. (2017) opined that library and information services to users in this digital age must improve information access to both physical and virtual users of the library. Okuongahe et al. (2018) itemised some of the services provided by academic libraries in Ekiti and Ondo States, Nigeria to include information and referral services, reference services, cataloguing and classification of library resources, charging and discharging of library materials and users' education services. Nwegbu (2015) identified the following as the services that an academic library should perform: organisation and maintenance of library collection in a way that users can easily access them, selecting adequate and suitable reference materials for the library and users, suggestions to users appropriate materials that may be useful for special purposes, education of users individually or as a group on how to use reference materials and various methods to access them, provision of reference materials to users who may not know how to search or those that just want a single word or sentence fact and teaching or guiding new or inexperienced readers on how to find resource.

Services like abstracting and indexing have been identified to be very important in academic libraries (Akanya, 2016). Jack (2015) revealed that reprographic especially in form of photocopying is a very essential service that an academic library should provide. Madu (2010) stated that selective dissemination of information is a very germane service within the academic library environment. This is packaging reference resources or services specially for researchers based on their specialty. Nwalo (2012) canvassed that bibliographic service is essential part of proper functioning of the academic library. It is the service that provides a list of related publications on a particular topic or subject for users' need. Mole (2014) pinpointed computer/online services as a must in the academic library environment. Corroborating this is the assertion of Nwalo (2012) that use of online search services will create opportunities for an expanded search over traditional academic reference services. Inter-library loan was also an important service rendered by academic libraries (Jack, 2015). Omoniwa (2016) stated that

information services delivery includes collection, synthesis and dissemination of up-to-date, unbiased, accurate, relevant information in different forms or formats such as books, bulletins, periodical, indexes, bibliographies, guide abstracts and other non-book formats that can be stored, retrieved and accessed when needed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Level of of knowledge sharing practices among staff working with polytechnic libraries in South-west, Nigeria

Written Contributions/Explicit knowledge		Weighted Mean = 2.50					
SN	Statement	A	F	O	N	\bar{X}	SD
1.	I submit documents and reports to my HOD	30(11.3%)	123(46.2%)	52(19.5%)	61(22.9%)	2.5414	.96748
2.	I publish articles in polytechnic journals, magazines, or newsletters	146(54.5%)	30(11.3%)	73(27.4%)	18(6.8%)	1.8647	1.03728
3.	I share documentation from personal files related to current work	93(35.0%)	70(26.3%)	51(19.5%)	52(19.5%)	2.5331	1.12861
4.	I contribute ideas and thoughts to library online social media pages and databases	22(8.3%)	91(34.3%)	105(39.5%)	48(18.0%)	2.6729	.86558
5.	I spend time in e-mail communication with others to help them with their work-related problems	91(34.2%)	123(46.2%)	0(0%)	52(19.5%)	2.6887	1.15328
Mean for explicit knowledge						2.4602	1.0305
Personal Interactions/Tacit knowledge							
6.	I support less-experienced colleagues with time from personal schedule guiding and counselling them	39(14.7%)	112(42.1%)	115(43.2%)	0(0%)	2.7143	70653
7.	I engage in long-term coaching relationships with junior/younger library staff	30(11.3%)	206(77.4%)	0(0%)	30(11.3%)	2.8872	74382
8.	I spend time in personal conversation (e.g., discussion in hallway, over lunch, through telephone) with others to help them with their work-related problems	48(18.0%)	96(36.1%)	60(22.6%)	62(23.3%)	2.4887	1.03971
9.	I keep others updated with important library information through personal conversation	40(15.0%)	134(50.4%)	62(23.3%)	30(11.3%)	2.6917	.86160
10.	I share passion and excitement on some specific subjects with others through personal conversation.	52(23.3%)	112(42.1%)	0(0%)	92(34.6%)	2.5414	1.18806
11.	I share experiences that may help others avoid risks and trouble through personal conversation	22(8.3%)	104(39.1%)	30(11.3%)	110(41.4%)	2.1429	1.05789
12.	I have online chats with others to help them with their work-related problems.	70(26.3%)	134(50.4%)	62(23.3%)	0(0%)	3.0301	.70513

13	I express ideas and thoughts in library meetings	60(22.6%)	206(77.4%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	3.2256	.41874
14	I participate fully in brainstorming sessions.	60(22.6%)	136(51.1%)	70(26.3%)	0(0%)	2.9624	.69939
15	I propose problem-solving suggestions in library meetings.	0(0%)	156(58.6%)	0(0%)	110(41.4%)	2.1729	.98679
16	I answer questions of others in library meetings.	40(15.0%)	104(39.1%)	60(22.6%)	62(23.3%)	2.4962	.78307
17.	I ask good questions that can elicit others' thinking and discussion in library meetings.	60(22.6%)	104(39.1%)	62(22.6%)	40(15.0%)	2.5414	1.18806
18.	I share success stories that may benefit the polytechnic in library meetings.	136(51.1%)	70(26.3%)	60(22.6%)	0(0%)	2.4586	1.00947
Mean for tacit knowledge						2.6426	.8760
GRAND MEANS						2.5514	.9532

The results on level of sharing explicit and tacit knowledge practices among polytechnic librarians in South-west, Nigeria is moderately high as shown in Table 1. This is reflected in the values of “always and often” which is higher than the other response formats frequency values and percentages. Similarly, the mean values of the four out of five items in this section were above the average weighted mean of 2.5. At the same time, the results show that the respondents’ knowledge-sharing practices based on personal interaction/tacit knowledge is high. The values of “always and often” in all the items in the section are higher than the other response formats’ frequency values and percentage. Also, the mean values of all the 13 items in this section were above the average weighted mean of 2.5.

RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

This section presents the results of formulated hypothesis tested to establish the relationship between the independent variables (knowledge-sharing practices) and the dependent variable (service delivery). The hypothesis is stated in the null form and tested at 0.05 level of significant.

H0: *There is no significant relationship between knowledge-sharing practices and service delivery among polytechnic library staff in South-west, Nigeria.*

Table 2: Relationship between Knowledge-sharing practices and Service Delivery

Variables	N	Mean	St. Dev	Df	R	P	Sig
Knowledge-sharing practices	266	46.1541	11.29914		.609	.000	Sig
Service Delivery	266	56.5188	9.06755	264			

Table 2 shows the relationship between knowledge-sharing practices and service delivery of polytechnic librarians in South-west Nigeria. Using product moment correlation, the finding reveals that knowledge-sharing practices ($r = .609$; $p < 0.05$) has a significant relationship with the service delivery of polytechnic library staff in South-west, Nigeria. This implies that there is a

positive linear relationship between knowledge-sharing practices and service delivery of staff working of polytechnic libraries in South-west Nigerian.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

The study reveals that the levels of knowledge-sharing practices are high and that the practices based on written contributions/explicit knowledge and personal interactions/tacit knowledge contributed to the high level of knowledge-sharing practices among staff in polytechnic libraries in the South-west, Nigeria. This finding is in accordance with the report of a study conducted by Awodoyin et al. (2016) which revealed that librarians in the selected academic libraries in Nigeria engaged in knowledge-sharing practices at a high level. The authors affirmed that despite the high level of infrastructural challenges, librarians still engaged in high level of knowledge-sharing practices among themselves. The finding of an international study that focused on knowledge-sharing practices among librarians at National University of Lesotho library in Southern Africa by Tahlero (2016) found that knowledge-sharing is a regular practice among the librarians. This also supports the finding in the current study that the knowledge-sharing practices of library staff are high. The similarity in the findings of the current study with the previous studies might be based on the fact that most organisations in the present day have realised the importance of knowledge as driver of an organisational success. This makes many of the organisations to be proactive in sharing knowledge and also take steps to encourage and motivate their employees to do same.

Contrary to the above is the study of Olayemi and Olayemi (2021) who reported the existence of a low level of knowledge-sharing practices among health science librarians in Africa. The study indicated that the main types of knowledge shared by respondents concerned conferences, workshops, and seminars; new trends and technologies in librarianship; newly acquired knowledge by the respondents; and scholarship availability. On the basis of this low level of knowledge-sharing practices among the health science librarians, the authors recommended that concerted efforts should be made to overcome barriers to knowledge-sharing practices within and across African countries. Similarly, Abubakar and Sahabi's (2022) study showed that librarians mostly used brainstorming and verbal discussions for knowledge-sharing practices among other knowledge-sharing tools, which implied that knowledge-sharing practices of librarians were low. The low level of knowledge-sharing behaviours in the above cases contrary to the researchers' current findings of high-level practices of knowledge-sharing might not be unconnected with minimal methods of knowledge-sharing practices adopted by the respondents concerned. To change the narrative, other methods of knowledge-sharing practices must be explored.

The hypothetical finding of the research revealed that knowledge-sharing practice has a significant relationship with the service delivery of polytechnic library staff in South-west, Nigeria. This implies that there is a positive linear relationship between knowledge-sharing practices and service delivery of staff working of polytechnic libraries in South-west Nigerian. This current finding corroborates that of Yusof and Ismail (2009) which reveals that there is a significant relationship between knowledge sharing and public sector service delivery. Similarly, it validates the finding of Osifade and Tunmibi (2025) who conducted a study on knowledge sharing and service delivery of librarians in public universities, Ogun State, Nigeria and reported that knowledge sharing has a significant influence on service delivery in the universities. The current finding is also in agreement with that of Imam and Ebiefung (2022) who conducted a

study on knowledge sharing as a determinant of information service delivery by library personnel in federal universities in South-West, Nigeria, it was found that knowledge sharing ($r = .561$; $p < 0.05$) has significant positive relationship with information service.

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

The study revealed that the levels of knowledge-sharing practices based on written contributions/explicit knowledge and personal interactions/tacit knowledge is high among staff in polytechnic libraries in the South-west, Nigeria. It was also established that knowledge-sharing practices has a significant relationship with the service delivery of polytechnic library staff in South-west, Nigeria

CONCLUSION

The study investigated knowledge-sharing practices as correlates of service delivery among polytechnic library staff in South-west, Nigeria and established that the respondents engaged in high level of sharing explicit (written) and tacit personal interaction) knowledge among themselves. It thus empirically established that knowledge-sharing practices have significant influence on service delivery of the staff of polytechnic libraries in South-west, Nigeria. Therefore, for sustainable service delivery in the polytechnic libraries, staff must not only endeavour to continue to engage more in knowledge sharing among themselves but must actually institute a culture of knowledge sharing practices to guarantee effective and efficient service delivery that will enable them deliver on their mandate of supporting teaching, learning and research efforts of the parent institutions.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In line with the above findings, it is hereby recommended that efforts should be made to encourage the practice of knowledge sharing among polytechnic library staff to preserve the knowledge in the various libraries and to facilitate efficient and effective service delivery that would guarantee provision of information services to users promptly, timely, reliably and satisfactorily. The current high rate of knowledge sharing practices among staff must not only be sustained but must be improved upon to ensure that the benefits and essence of knowledge sharing which is aimed at improving service delivery is achieved.

REFERENCES

- Abdulsalam, J. A, Babarinde, B. A. & Osalusi, M. A (2025). Knowledge sharing and research output of librarians in federal. In N. M. Mnjama, O. O. Oladokun & T. L Mosweu (Eds.), *strengthening information and knowledge management paradigms in the era of advanced technologies: proceedings of the 5TH biennial conference 2025* (pp. 256-270). DLIS, University of Botswana.
- Abubakar, A. H. & Sahabi, M. K. (2022). Knowledge-sharing practices and service delivery by professional librarians in Ahmadu Bello University Library, Zaria. *Sapientia Foundation Journal of Education, Sciences and Gender Studies*, 4(2), 95-104.

- Akanya, J. (2016). Delinquent readership problems in academic libraries in Enugu State. *Borno Library, Archival and Information Science Journal*, 31(2), 3-32.
- Andreeva, T., & Kianot, A. (2012). Does knowledge management really matter? Linking knowledge management practices, competitiveness and economic performance. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 16(4), 617-636. <https://doi.org/10.1108/13673271211246185>.
- Antara, K., Khaled, R., & Elhadj, A. (2024). The impact of knowledge sharing on the performance of employees in the Algerian public sector. *International Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 18(7), 1036–1056. Retrieved from <https://ijeponline.org/index.php/journal/article/view/612>.
- Awodoyin, A., Osisanwo, T., Adetoro, N., & Adeyemo, I. (2016). Knowledge-sharing behaviour pattern analysis of academic librarians in Nigeria. *Journal of Balkan Libraries Union*, 4(1), 12-19.
- Bessick, J. & Naicker, V. (2013). Barriers to tacit knowledge retention: An understanding of the perceptions of the knowledge management of people inside and outside the organisation. *South African journal of information management* 15(2), 1-8. <http://www.sajim.co.za/index.php/SAJIM/article/viewFile/556/646>.
- Imam, Y. & Ebiefung, R. (2022). Knowledge sharing as a determinant of information service delivery by library personnel in federal universities in South-West, Nigeria" (2022). *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*. 6930. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/6930>.
- Islam, M. A., Agarwal, N. K., & Ikeda, M. (2014). Library adoption of knowledge management using Web 2.0 a new paradigm for libraries. *International Federation of Library Associations (IFLA) journal*, 40(4), 317-330.
- Izu, L .O. (2020). *Knowledge sharing among staff at Delta State University Library Abraka for improved service provision. Project submitted for the degree of masters in the subject Information Science at the University of South Africa, Pretoria.* <http://hdl.handle.net/10500/27251>.
- Jack, O. (2015). Attitudes toward computers: When do they predict computer use? *Information and Management*, 34(5). http://southernlibrarianship.icaap.org/content/v08n02/tella_a01.html.
- Lin, H. F. (2015). Linking knowledge management orientation to balance scorecard outcomes. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 19(6), 1-53.
- Ma, Z., Huang, Y., Wu, J., Dong, W., & Qi, L. (2014). What matters for knowledge-haring in collectivistic cultures? Empirical evidence from China. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 18(5), 1004-1019.
- Madu, O. E. (2010). Book theft and mutilation and their effects on the services of the Benue State Polytechnic library. *The Electronic Library*. 28(4) 555-567. www.emeraldinsight.com/0264-0473.html.
- Maina, J., Masese, J. M., George, B. O., & Makwae, E. N. (2017). Usage and user satisfaction of library resources in Kisii University Library, Kenya. *International Journal of Library and Information Science Studies*, 3(3), 20-29.
- Martins, N. & Ledimo, O. (2015). The perceptions and nature of service delivery innovation among government employees: An exploratory study. *Journal of Governance and Regulation*, 4(4). <https://info@virtusinterpress.org>.

- Mole, P. (2014). Delinquent readers: A study of the problem in university libraries. <http://program.unl.edu/libphilprac/593>.
- Nwalo, H. (2012). *User Education in academic libraries: Students' use of academic library*. London: Library Association Publishing Limited.
- Nwegbu, E. L. (2015). Electronic information access and utilization by Makerere University in Uganda. Retrieved from <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/2-0/>.
- Okuongahe, O. O., Ijeh, C. I., & Erhabor, J. O. (2018). User delinquency as a factor affecting effective service delivery in university libraries in Ekiti and Ondo States, Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*, 1701. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/1701>.
- Olayemi, O. M. & Olayemi, K. J. (2021). Knowledge-sharing practices among African health sciences librarians. *Journal of Medical Librarians Association*, 109(4), 624-630. doi: 10.5195/jmla.2021.1183.
- Osifade, M. S. & Tunmibi, S. (2025). Knowledge sharing and service delivery of librarians in public universities, Ogun State, Nigeria. *Lead City International Journal Of Library, Information & Communication Sciences [LCIJLICS]*, 2(1).
- Oyoo, M. O. (2019). Role of knowledge sharing cultures on competitive advantage: A review of the non-financial dimension. *The International Journal of Humanities & Social Studies*. <http://doi.org/10.24940/theijhss/2019/v7/i9/hs1909-059>.
- Razmerita, L., Kirchner, K., & Nielsen, P. (2016). What factors influence knowledge-sharing in organisations? A social dilemma perspective of social media communication. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 20(6), 1225-1246.
- Santosh, S. & Panda, S. (2016). Sharing of Knowledge among Faculty in a Mega Open University. *Open Praxis* 8 (3) 247-264. *International Council for Open and Distance Education*. <https://www.learntechlib.org/p/173539/>.
- Shehab, S., Al-Bsheish, M., Meri, A., Dauwed, M., Aldhmadi, B. K., Kareem, ... Jarrar, M. (2023). Knowledge sharing behaviour among head nurses in online health communities: The moderating role of knowledge self-efficacy, 18(1). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0278721>.
- Tahlero, T. E. (2016). *Improving service delivery at the national university of Lesotho library through knowledge-sharing*. Master thesis. University of South Africa. xi, 150. <http://hdl.handle.net/10500/217>.
- Vij, S. & Farooq, R. (2014). Knowledge-sharing orientation and its relationship with business performance: A structural equation modeling approach”, *The IUP Journal of Knowledge Management*, 12(3), 17-41.
- Wang, Z. & Wang, N. (2012). Knowledge-sharing, innovation and firm performance. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 39(10), 8899-8908. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2012.02.017>.
- Wang, Z., Sharma, P. N., & Cao, J. (2016). From knowledge-sharing to firm performance: A predictive model comparison. *Journal of Business Research*, 69(2016), 4650-4658. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2016.03.055>.
- Zamiri, M. & Ali, E. (2024). Methods and technologies for supporting knowledge sharing within learning communities: A systematic literature review. *Administrative Sciences* 14(17). <https://doi.org/10.3390/admsci14010017>.

- Wen, J., & Ma, R. (2021). Antecedents of knowledge hiding and their impact on organisational performance, *Frontiers in Psychology, Frontiers Media SA*.
<http://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.796976>.
- Yaya, J. A. & Adeeko, K. (2024). Analytical factors boosting service delivery among staff in academic libraries: A review of the literature. *IAFOR Journal of Literature & Librarianship, 139(1)*.
- Yusof, Z. M. & Ismail, M. B. (2009). Is there a relationship between knowledge sharing practice and the quality of service delivery? A case study in three government agencies in Malaysia. *Journal of Knowledge Management Practice*. Retrieved from <https://journals.klalliance.org/index.php/JKMP/article/view/296>.